

KEY INDICATORS

With 597,204 hectares, Sweden had 19.9% of its farmland under organic management and therefore the third-highest organic area share in the European Union, well above that of the EU (10.6%). Growth from 2001-2022 almost trebled and was thus lower compared to other EU countries. With 3,855 million euros, Sweden had the sixth-largest market in the European Union, and 8.2 percent of all food sales were organic, constituting one of the highest retail sales shares in the European Union.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

202,827 ha (6.6%)

597,204 ha (19.9%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

194%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

167,546 ha (10.3%)

460,387 ha (18.1%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

282 ha (3.8%)

732 ha (21%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

35,000 ha (7.6%)

136,085 ha (29.4%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

3,589 (4.4%)

5,079 (8.6%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

N/D

Processors

540

1,093

Importers

121

310

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

225 M €

2,607 M € (8.2%)

Per Capita Consumption

25.3 €

247.8 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

1,059 %

Imports

N/D

153,328 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN SWEDEN

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, based on Eurostat, Jordbruksverket and Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN SWEDEN

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on various sources including Statistics Sweden, Ekoweb, Ekologiska Lantbrukarna

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Sweden CAP strategic plan provides for a 23% increase in supported organic area, with a significant proportion of certified organic land, mainly grassland, not receiving support directly for being organic, but still eligible for other agri-environmental support. The planned expenditure on organic farming is set to fall by 2027 compared with 2018, with a decrease of 21% in the average payment per ha supported, despite a slight increase in payment rates per ha for different land uses. The decrease in the planned average support rate is assumed to be a result of a different balance between horticultural and other crops planned. There is no additional support for conversion compared with maintenance payments.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

	2018	2027
Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	355 kha	437 kha (+23%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	11.8%	14.5% (+23%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	58%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	75 M€	73 M€ (-3%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	211 €	167 € (-21%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

	2023-2027	ORGANIC SHARE*
Organic Farming Support (P1)*	351 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	680 M€	23.1%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	840 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	6,020 M€	5.8%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	151	142	472	708
	2023	P1	177	147	492	737
Change from 2019 to 2023			+17%	+4%	+4%	+4%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	151	142	472	708
	2023	P1	177	147	492	737
Change from 2019 to 2023			+17%	+4%	+4%	+4%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019	P2	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2023	P1	0%	0%	0%	0%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Sweden has had multiple organic action plans dating back to 1996. At 30%, Sweden has one of the highest share of land area targets in the EU, starting from a strong base. The 2021 certified organic area share (20.2 %) and the market share (8.9%) exceeded the previous action plan targets. It also has ambitious targets for organic share of public procurement. A significant focus of the plans is on training and information initiatives at all levels, including for staff and others engaged in public procurement and catering.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2011-13	20% of UAA by 2013	6% of market by 2013 / 25% of public procurement
Current Action Plan	2018-30	30% of UAA by 2030	60% of public procurement

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2011 - 2013)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2018 - 2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Sweden is negligible. Sweden was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. As the funding, if any, is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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